

Portrayal of Capitalist's Dire Impact on the Environment and the Relationship between Man and Nature in Dhruv Bhatt's *Oceanside Blues (Samudrantike)*

Dr. Ashok M. Hulibandi
Professor, Department of English
Karnatak University, Dharwad-580003

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Abstract: This paper highlights the theme of nature and man's relationship in Dhruv Bhatt's *Oceanside Blues (Samudrantike)*. Dhruv Bhatt's *Oceanside Blues* is in the form of memories of a young Civil engineer, who was deputed to survey an arid coastal part of Saurashtra. It depicts that the capitalists in the name of civilization have resulted in dire impacts towards the environment and the relationship between man and nature. The materialistic civilization introduces which persists in the form of global imperialism. It has led man towards the path to butcher mother earth to plunder resources for his benefit. It is also depicts an exploitation of tribal land in the name of civilization, it is not a recent phenomenon, and it is a long-lived tradition passed down by the colonizers as the fiction of national progress. The notions of civilization, progress and development modeled on the dictums of the western thought are also deconstructed within the framework of tribal ecological consciousness.

Full-length Paper:

Dhruv Bhatt's *Oceanside Blues* is originally published in Gujarati, was published in 1993. Vinod Meghani has translated it into English. Dhruv Bhatt was born on 8 May 1947 in Ningala village of Bhavanagar, Gujarati state. He studied at various places, he studies 1 to 4 standard at Jafrabad, Matriculation

from Keshod, after studying commerce for two years, and he left further studies. In 1972, he joined Gujarat Machine Manufacturers as a sales supervisor, he voluntarily took retirement and started writing career. He married Divya Bhatt; his son Devavrat was born in 1976 and his daughter Shivani in 1980. He wrote the followings literary works *Lovely Pan House* (2012), *Khovayelu Nagar* (1984), *Agnikanya* (1988), *Samudrantike* (1993), *Tattvamasi* (1998), *Atarapi* (2001), *Karnalok* (2005), *Akoopar* (2011), *Timirpanthi* (2015) and *Gay Tena Geet* (2003) and *Shrunvantu* are poetry collections. Vindo Meghani is a translator in English and Gujarati. He translated *Earthen Lamps*, *Mansaiva* and *Salagatan Sarajmukhi*.

Dhruv Bhatt's *Oceanside Blues* is in the form of memories of a young Civil engineer, who was deputed to survey an arid coastal part of Saurashtra. It depicts that the capitalists in the name of civilization have resulted in dire impacts towards the environment and the relationship between man and nature. The materialistic civilization introduces which persists in the form of global imperialism. It has led man towards the path to butcher mother earth to plunder resources for his benefit. It also depicts an exploitation of tribal land in the name of civilization, it is not a recent phenomenon, and it is a long-lived tradition passed down by the colonizers as the fiction of national progress. The notions of civilization, progress and development modeled on the dictums of the western thought are also deconstructed within the framework of tribal ecological consciousness. Ecocriticism attempts to transcend the duality of art and life, human and the natural, and explore the interconnections between them. In this respect, eco-criticism takes into account varied literary, ecological and philosophical perspectives. *Oceanside Blues* is set in the coastal region of Saurashtra, it is an account of a civil engineer, who has been assigned the task of surveying the land to establish a chemical factory in the tribal region. Dhruv Bhatt has been regarded as a remarkable writer known for establishing a

discourse on the current environmental issues faced by the world by fictionalizing them and questioning the 'cynical, profit-driven economy'. Several environmental issues have been interwoven in the novel like the conflict between human and wildlife, the encroachment of forest areas and resulting concerns in livelihood and access to the forest for resources to survive, forestry management, illegal mining, ecological imperialism, and climate change etc.

The novel begins with the description of a Young Civil Engineer's memory. He had a wonderful experience and it portrait the relationship between man and environment and how man destroyed nature for his selfishness. It depicts Civil Engineer's real experience; he travelled two days by a metre gauge coach and reached his workplace. He was waiting for the Ebb; he saw a girl named Janaki, was plying near the lighthouse. Ismail welcomed him; a clerk a young Civil Engineer. Civil Engineer reached the bungalow; he travelled by a bullock cart from Patwa or by a ferry. Clerk tried to comfort him in various ways because his superior officer has ordered him to arrange transport to him, he asked, "What do we do, then? The clerk replied, "No, both I shall arrange it somehow" (Bhatt 3). A clerk arranged accommodation at the lighthouse quarters until transport to be arranged. Ismail picked up engineer's belongings. On the way to reach the lighthouse quarters, he saw "the parent, top half of his body bare interrupted his chore and sauntered to the well" (Bhatt 5). He draw a bucket of water from the well and gave it him, he asked him, "Where ye live?" "Afar. I am spending tonight at the light house. Tomorrow I shall go to the estate bungalow" (Bhatt 5-6). Janaki and her mother welcomed him. Vaal-baai is kind hearted lady, she said, "What mates you fidgety, eh? We are not short of a thing ere. The yard is spacious and vacant, all yours. Stay ere all you want" (Bhatt 7). It was surprised to him; she was not bother to seek consent of anyone not even of her husband before asking im to stay there. Vaal-baai asked her daughter, "to draw some water from the well for him to bath. Then take him to

Shikot or Shrine” (Bhatt 7). Young Civil Engineer bathed and walked towards the temple. Young Engineer and Janaki have been discussed about other matters.

The novelist depicts the innocence and helping nature of villagers. Janaki said, “Let’s go. Now we will make it” (Bhatt 9). Janaki walked very fast, she continued and said, “If you are scared, just grab my hand and hold on to it” (Bhatt 9). She sing a song; then, they reached the shrine and spend sometime there. There was a dusk, when they returned to the orchard. That night, under the moon light, Vaal-baai, a poor peasant, and his homemaker who has not known to him at until a few hours back, she served a meal without wanting to know even his name. He enjoyed a food and stayed that night with the peasant family at the Orchard. He was feeling that Janaki was an old aged friend. He bidding farewell to Janaki, Vaal-baa was very painful to him, and he has developed strong an affinity with them. He woke up early in the morning, Vaal-baai was in the process of igniting the stove, and she served him a brass saucer brimming with a tea and said, “Saboor’ll be going toward estate bungalow, today he will take you along if you wish” (Bhatt 12). Saboor was standing near the compound wall; he was about twenty-five. He went and fetched him; he said, “How do we go? By cart or by a fishing boat?” (Bhatt 12). They completed meal, and he bear farewell to Janaki’s Orchard. The oarsman, Saboor and Engineer moved. Saboor is a well culture, his taught, “One treat a stranger as an old friend and a chatter with him endlessly” (Bhatt 14). He walked slowly, he did not speak anything, he asked about his home and parents, Saboor replied with painfully, “In last famine, both went to work as labourers at relief sites that provided jobs to starving. Ma didn’t come back. Old; man did and died at home” (Bhatt 15). Engineer put his hand on Saboor’s shoulder and consoled him, but Saboor cannot control his emotions, and he asked him, “How can anyone live on empty belly?” (Bhatt 15). There was terrible heat, they

cannot walk, and they take rest there. Engineer opened his bag and gave some biscuits and sweets. He enquired about the bungalow, Saboor replied, “No, problem. Everything’s there” (Bhatt 17). Sarvan is a watchman, other staff members also there. Engineer introduced himself. “I am Engineer with vast executive powers, would also have to carry out petty clerical chores, and those too for a pittance of a salary. Devil must have possessed me and led me to the disposal destiny” (Bhatt 18). Khera and Patwa are small towns near that place. They walked nearly two and half an hour to reach bungalow. When they reached a bungalow, security guard received them whole-heartedly. Security guard served a tea and arranged accommodation.

Oceanside Blues depicts the relationship between human being and nature and greedy of a man. Engineer woke up early morning and stepped out into the corridor. He asked Sarver, “Shall we go to the harbour town and fetch groceries today?” he replied, “Not today. Need a cart. It comes every eight days with a mail. We can walk to Patwa and returned by that cart” (Bhatt 21). He remembered the last days experience especially with Janaki and her mother. He thought that Sabar was his guide; he had hardly ascended a couple of steps of the stair. He saw a tall and slim woman; she was holding a broom in one hand descending the stain and said, “We are collecting rain water in the terrace for the coming year. Please don’t go upstairs with your shoes on” (Bhatt 23). He stopped to move, he sat down on the parapet and watched the sea, and then he returned to his office. A visitor come along with Kabir, a horse, he introduced himself ‘I’m Naaran have brought the horse from main harbour” (Bhatt 26). The government has set a horse to boost her staff, Naaran taught the riding, an Engineer said, “But can’t ride. “Can learn. Not difficult. This Kabir, my fond one, is after all an animal of breed. You need to nothing but keep sitting on the back; he had do rest” said Naaran” (Bhatt 27). Aval served a meal, they enjoyed a meal, Naaran took him to a beach. It is his first experienced to walk on ocean

at night. An Engineer sat on a big rock and enjoyed. Sarvan asked, “Shall we go home now?” (Bhatt 28). They stepped out of the water and they walked back towards to a bungalow. On the way, when they entered into a dark shadows cluster of babul trees, they saw someone was coming in their direction. Engineer asked, “Who’s that?” (Bhatt 28). He replied that he is Noor-bhaai, he said, “This forest department of yours is a big sham! Over there, in deep jungle, timber’s felled and stolen by cartloads and here in bitter barren salty plains you are guarding babul shrubs!” (Bhatt 28). Noor bhaai replied, “Brother mine” (Bhatt 28). Noor-bhaai met them, and then they reached a bungalow. Next morning, met Noormammad, he wears khaki dress. He planted babul trees, now they have grown. Noor-bhaai was expanding with tiny and tender creation of nature. He shown many birds, especially Doodhraaj is very beautiful bird. His heart suddenly grew heavy with sadness and he felt that, “The entire system needed a complete change. Education should mean teaching to love nature. A system that can produce many more Noor-bhaais should be evolved. Man too should be able to inspire in birds and beasts the same confidence and trust that the black drongo inspire in the similar birds” (Bhatt 33). He was thinking about who will bring to change.

Oceanside Blue depicts the Government project’s proposal. Proposals are anti-nature and now they destroyed nature. Sunday is a holiday for government offices, the office would not opened that day. Sarvan would go to the city, buy provisions, and pick up mail. They received a letter about to start survey the land surrounding Khera. Sarvan carries some documents on a donkey, he started to walk along with Kabir, and he returned from Khera. The first rain of the season came in the beginning of June; Noor-bhaai appeared at the bungalow. They have discussed about birds especially Doodhraj and nature. One day, Saboor came near the corridor steps, Engineer asked, “Do you need something?” he asked “You are selling land”. Engineer said, “Who told you I

was selling land?” “Sarvan said I talk with you” (Bhatt 46). Engineer was unhappy, people will misunderstand him and he said, “The land belongs to the government, my duty is to tell the government if this land is good for setting up factories. I am not selling land” (Bhatt 46). He explained true things, he was appointed to survey the land for setting up a chemical zone there. The government policy is that before start the factory, they would start to be the growing of trees around the planned chemical zone and he convinced him.

Oceanside Blues depicts the rituals of a costal belt and the government project. Monsoon ended, Diwaali festival passed. Saboor did not return. Engineer asked Sarvan about Saboor, he replied that he has neither a home nor a family. He put up the open wherever he found work. Engineer is engaged in his work, the blueprint of the green belt proposal was approved by the head office. An entire area of the prepared green belt was approved and was handed over to the forest department for planting and rearing babul and other inferior types of trees. One day, Saboor came and met an Engineer, he suddenly felt like giving him good news, he said, “Write an application for plot of land and give it to me” (Bhatt 50). During the fieldwork Saboor and Sarvan helped him, Engineer assigned work to Saboor, and he has agreed to do. Next day, Engineer reached the Southern border of the terriers on the peak of a huge precipice. Saboor was waiting for him. He spreads out the maps on the surface and examines them minutely. He knew that it is only free land in the Southern part. He inspects the land and they returned to the bungalow. He explained to Saboor the reality of the present situation, “Saboor, it’s true that without paying money one cannot get good land; but don’t you see that this is not land? Black slab of sheer granite it is! The government allot land on the condition that trees should be grown on it. You won’t be permitted to start a quarry there. I tried to put it as Simple as I could” (Bhatt 53). But there is no good response from him. An engineer controlled himself and said, “Look I can help you with some cash. I’ll purchase

for you a plot of land elsewhere may be not large enough to raise a crop but where you can built a hut and grow vegetables. What do you say?” (Bhatt 53). Saboor did not utter any word. Saboor was dreaming that, “prefers to live and even die, on his own land” (Bhatt 53). Saboor was happy, but he cannot write and read. Aval came and serve smoothly to him. She was smiling and said, “He can’t write! Let me write for him. I shall take his thumbprint when he’s back” (Bhatt 55). Engineer laughed and said, “Very weak. You go home I shall write it for him” (Bhatt 55). Saboor was so happy. Next day he visits to Shyaal Island, then, he returned to a bungalow. He noticed that a child was sitting on the corridor step, he was watching tin pot lying on the well basin’s lying wall, An engineer asked, “And who are you, son?”

‘Vishoo,’ he said with smile.

‘Do you know me?’ I asked my young visitor.

‘I do! You rode Kabir to Patwa!’

‘Yes’

‘My home’s in Patwa, he said and added another clue to his identity. ‘I’m a pal of Noor-*Chaacha*’

‘Indeed, you know Noor-bhaai well?’

‘Sure. He one gave me a ride. Also took me bird-watching! ‘Noor-bhaai seemed to have infected the child too with the charm of the winged ones” (Bhatt 58-59). Child is relative of Aval. The novelist depicts the rituals of coastal area. They get bath in a sea and purify themselves. Elderly couple had come to a bungalow; Engineer asked them, “Though I’m rather worried. Having endured a bullock cart journey this for at her age, she might take ill”. A elderly woman as companion, “We didn’t want to bring her along but for the last three days she had been insisting that she had bathe in the sea on this non-moon day, no matter how” (Bhatt 61). No doubt, an old woman took a risk to take bath in the ocean on this particular day. On that day, several young women and young men get a

holy bath. An engineer was delighted and feeling of oneness with them. An old woman was in rapture; whenever a wave approached and passed by the chair and she searched her arms wide on it, she was receiving the ocean in her embrace. There was a big competition and adventure games like clinging to wooden plank and riding over a rolling surf right up to the sandy shore. An engineer was participated in all the games, he felt reborn and he could mingle with folks. Vishnoo was sitting by his side, and he hugged him.

Oceanside Blues depicts fisherman's life and their philosophy. A young engineer has decided go to Shyaal Island from Varaah Swaroop. Aval is a good decision maker, she speaks resolutely and briefly. Finally, she has selected Krishno Tandel, he is husband of Beli. Aval know that, Krishno is good sailor. Aval is not a friend but she packed everything to him. Next morning, he came with a boat. He had proveded his seamship by making the boat ride flood tide rollers and deftly steering her through the reef-strews ocean in the dark night all the way up to the bungalow. They boarded the boat and took their seat, his boat moved slowly. He was very good Sailor, he applied all his strength pushing the pole against the rocks and then slid the boat slowly out of the reefs. Krishno narrates his experience that, "Real fun of sailing the sea is at night" (Bhatt 70). They were strongly believed in an Ocean god, he asked him "You want to sail her?" (Bhatt 70). He was willing to sail a boat. He was following Krishno's instructions. He learned the first lesson from him. Why they sail a boat everyone should be honest, otherwise dangerous will occur. There was something happen, Engineer said, "For a few moments. I thought you had really fallen overboard. Anxiety made me panicky"

Krishno's face suddenly turned grim. He looked at me and said coldly, "At Sea one never tell a lie"

'Why do you say that?'

‘Fancy you asking why! If you were worried, why didn’t! you jumps into a sea to rescue me? Look there! Do you see rope under the plank?’ Why didn’t you throw it into Sea?’ (Bhatt 73). Boat was glided smoothly, Krishno came over and sat near him, Krishno said, “I don’t blame you for what you did. It’s tough being to Sea all alone, and you have proved a worthy sailor. All I wanted to tell you was that out at sea, too there are ethics. When someone goes overboard, sailor” must jump into sea to save without thinking of own safety. That’s the law laid down by sea” (Bhatt 73). The boat moved slowly, the Shyaal Island was visible from distance place. It is an archipelago of three Islands. A small creek east of the main Island separated it from a smaller islet that housed two green painted dargaahs, a lighthouse and its quarters, Krishno saw a rock islet, he did not speak for a moment, and he sad, “It is not an islet. It’s Bhensala, a holm, Boats can’t move there. An engineer asked him, “What is Bhensala? What does it mean? He replied, “*Bensala-Pir* is called an enshrined ocean deity” (Bhatt 76). They went up to the rocks and stepped on the soil of the Island, and they advanced eastward towards the smaller isle. They went to the light house; they saw four to five young men are sitting on its concrete varandah. They welcome them, and they introduced themselves and they explained their programme. An engineer stayed in the lighthouse, Kishno left. Next day, Krishno came, An engineer woke up early, they walked up to the dargaah and met Fakir. Krishno came to the dargaah paid obeisance to the shrine with joined palms. There was a wonderful thing, nobody touch anything. The quarters also carried no locks but only fastening chain. They set out of the Island, they sailed an hour and entered the Island. There was a worst condition of fisherman’s life. There were roars of fisherman’s thatched huts starting from the wharf and extended for on the eyes could reach. The death fishes were laid for dry to the sun. They went up on ascent reach the highest point of the Island. There were only fisherman, an engineer asked Krishno, “Although you’re

fisherman, not a former, why do you live inland? He said, “My long stay in the region had helped me identify a peculiarity of these people: those who earned their livelihood by sailing and fishing did not associate themselves with land in any way, those who lived tilling and ploughing the earth preferred to live away from the seashore” (Bhatt 79). Krishno shows him crabs, starfish and tiny seahorses hiding on the holes under the sand. They reached to lighthouse shore, Krishno turned back and paced across the creek to the main Island.

Oceanside Blues depicts the relationship between tribles and the nature, their life of tribal. Engineer was waiting for arrived of Krishno but he did not turn-up. They had a plan to visit his house and then walk to the seashore of the main Island. He gave some instructs to Dayaraam that, “If Krishno comes tell him to meet me at the wharf” (Bhatt 81). He crossed the creek; he walked along the seashore all the way to the Wharf. He walked towards the Wharf on a path that was flanked by small and dainty lush green orchards. There were many farms, small houses were built. When he was walking through orchard, he saw an old man was sitting on a cot in the front yard and smoking a hookah. An engineer asked him, “Grand-pa, what crop are you growing?” he replied “Tikam? He wondered he has not heard of a name of a crop and he was more curious. There was a young woman from behind the cottage, she spoke loudly, “Grand-pa! He is not asking your name! He wants to know what we are growing” (Bhatt 82). He replied, “Ho..ho..ho.. heartilly laughed the old man “Bonti we’ve planted here. And *baayato* at the rear. That’s all that had grown ere. No other grain does grow” (Bhatt 82). An engineer was looking at the stem of the plant, it is inferior food grain. When he was examining everything, it create suspicious in the mind of old man and others, the old man asked, “New on Island”?

“Yes” I said glancing at the young woman

‘Deviti, my son’s daughter’, the old man introduced her, ‘On her first visit to parents home after her marriage’ (Bhatt 82). An old man was intimate with him and narrating his family background. The old man asked him “From where?” “From the estate bungalow”. Trikam asked him, “Who sailed you here?” “Krishno, Krishno Tandel sailed me here” (Bhatt 83). Trikam realised that Krishno brought him there. An engineer feels that, there was a mysterious seem to be surrounding, he think that “Why can’t one stay on Bhensala at night?” Deviki said “Never mind nights” (Bhatt 84). It is real thing that no one has dared to sail even a daytime to there. These tribes believe that Bhensala is a great deity. An engineer asked “Whose abode is this Bhensala rock?” ‘Ocean’s believed to be a pir, a deity manifest; just as every prison has a home. Ocean too has a home, deep, very deep down, in neither world” (Bhatt 84). Trikam narrates many thing, especially the relationship between man and nature; they treat nature as a god and supreme. An old man narrates the power of deity, “Pir is a deity. In His abode when He stands revealed before a human being, none known if He’d be mighty pleased or become raving mad. If pleased, He’d gratify the intruder” (Bhatt 84). An engineer first put a blind faith in Bhensala, he remember his grandmother narrates many folk tales.Devita was great support of her grandfather. Engineer collects information about Krishno. On the way, he met Beli, who is wife of Krishno, Beli said “Out sailing” (Bhatt 88). He was angry, anyhow Engineer arranged someone to sail. But he is not willing to go without Krishno, he is willing to waiting for him. Engineer has decided to return to Beli’s farmhouse, she was sitting under a Limada tree and cleaning a gunmetal platter with clay. Beli treats him as her own brother, she served meal. Engineer praised Beli’s husband Krishno he is very brave and bold. She asked him, “How do you know?” (Bhatt 91). Engineer tells his experience on a seashore. Beli did not say anything; she finished her eating in silently, then

cleaned up and put away things in their respective places. She dragged a cot under the Limada tree for him to sit. Engineer asked to Beli about Bhensala. Beli narrates the power of Bhensala, “About twenty odd years ago it was. Probably sometime during the fourth year of our marriage. I once came down with fever. It persisted. Elders said someone’d posed me” (Bhatt 91). Krishno did not believe but he took her to hospital and took a medicine. Beli cried and said to him, “Don’t call the Voodooman If you don’t want but at least make a resolve, even if it is to make me feel better!” (Bhatt 92). Immediately, he vowed to offer a coconut to Sea-God if got well. Beli’s nervous, fingers kept scrawling on the ground while she spoke. ‘And I was on my feet in no time’ “The vowed worked! ‘I said in a jocular tone’ ‘After I got well, we waited for an auspicious day to go to sea shore to offer coconut to a Ocean Pir” (Bhatt 92). Engineer believed that Beli’s experience and he feel what Beli must have gone through that night. There was a good relationship between Krishno and Beli, he would not believe other’s vows on her husband Beli was so angry on Krishno, she scolds him because he has not turn up. When she asked him, he stood up and said, “I’m on my way. If I don’t deliver coconut to Pir tonight, call me a bastard” (Bhatt 92). Krishno started to fulfill his offer to the Ocean Pir, Krishno and his father recall but his father-in-law could not stopped him then he disappeared. Beli and others went to dargaah and kept looking for the light of skiff but there is no clue. Beli continued adventures of Krishno, “At that moment I decided that if he came to harm I’ll dream myself in the sea.’ ‘When a glimmer of light was sighted on Bhensala rock, we all sighted relief and returned to pier. We sat there waiting all night, but Krishno did not returned. Next day, sailors turned the surrounding waters upside down and searching for him but no, sign of him or his skiff’. ‘After three days he was found sprawled in ravine; all mangled and bloodied he was. Couldn’t recognize anyone; won’t utter a word. Fakir-baapa carried him to dargaah and for fifteen days kept him

there, all alone. Dargaah was cordoned off to stop anyone approaching Krishno. After a month, fakir-baapu himself brought Krishno to island. On that day, we shifted our house away from a seashore and I made Krishno swear that he would never sail. On a long voyage, and would farm instead” (Bhatt 93). Beli stood up, went inside the house, and returned with an earthen pot. He drank water and he went to lighthouse residency. Shyaal is a beautiful place; there was an abundance of natural beauty. Dayaaram was busy cleaning the lighthouse. Krishno did not turned up, Engineer reached Beli’s farm house and met her, and he said “Beli I will go away tomorrow’ ‘Don’t want to stay till Tandel comes back? He’d sail you back to the mainland, she said ‘I’d be late. When Krishno return, send a word with one of the shepherds. I’d come back, time permitting” (Bhatt 100). Engineer was sitting at fishermen’s wharf and waiting for the fishing boat that was to sail to the mainland. He has to wait an hour to arrival of a boat. He walked nearly township, he wondered around the shop and spotted a pile of colorful sashes in a corner. Engineer is very kind hearted, he felt like buying one for Beli. It is first time buying one for Beli. It is first occasion of buying a gift for a woman. He went to near Beli’s farmhouse but he did not find her. He met a boy and requested, ‘Will you do something for me? Give this to Beli when she returns and tell her that her brother from the lighthouse brought this for her’ (Bhatt 103). A boy asked surprised, “Then why give it to me?” he replied. ‘through it under her door-chain. ‘His ‘innocence sparkled at me, ‘Here no one’d take it. Just leave it at her door” (Bhatt 103). Engineer returned to the wharf, the boat had already berthed. He reached Vaaraaroop. There was a beautiful Varaah temple, he get blaming.

Oceanside Blue depicts the capitalist nature of greedy and destroyed nation in the name of development. Noor-bhaai met an engineer and shared his experienced and his views on establishing chemical factory. He was concern on nation and they started a long journey. Noor-bhaai showed peacocks, they

climbed a large rock from there, they saw flock of peacocks. He saw peacocks are eating aquatic creatures. Noor Bhaai said the truth, if they started chemical factory, “The salty plains has turned so barren and infertile that the peacock, an angelic bird, had to struggle up and down the seashore rocks for survival. The land had, probably forever, lost its sap, its well to live. Remnant, if any, would be consumed by the factories producing chemicals. It would not be staying back to witness of the fate of Banyan” (Bhatt 107). Noor-Bhaai is very unhappy, he speaks man’s grandness, “Brutality of man on this universe’s no less than fiendish. If he had his way, he’d suck dry his mother’s breasts” (Bhatt 107). Then, they ride the upper trail. They saw green angles and he was narrating the history of the region. It was ruled by a King, his father was a guard employee. He studied an old record, this Havel is not belongs to the kingdom, it was ruled by the British Agency. But tribble said, “It belonged to Almighty” (Bhatt 109). Kings and Nawaab are foraged this patch whenever they wanted. Noor Bhaai tell the story of Haada Bhatt of Patwa, he joined the forest department and he made the whole area barren land. An Engineer thinks that Aval must be relative of Hada Bhatt, they reached bungalow Vishnu asked Noor-bhaai and an engineer. “Noor uncle why didn’t you take me with you”? Noor-uncle took him for a walk.

Oceanside Blues depicts the beauty and defaulted accurate of Shayaad Island Bhensala rock and Haada Bhatt. Engineer wrote a detail letter to Panaasher and Veena. He has plan to meet Baawajiji, he met him and he welcomed him, “welcome, friend enjoyed your stay on Island?” (Bhatt 118). He replied very positively, they have been discussing about change in the Island. Baawaj read a detail report on Island and he narrates evolution of the earth, he said, “Listen. There was a time when earth did not exist. Then too native existed. When earth was born, a ball of fire it was. Then came water, seaweeds and plants. They also perished only to be reborn. Nature is always

absolute unconfined. No one can ever fetter it or foul it. Get that into your head. Then go ahead and write what you will. You must carry out yours task” (Bhatt 120). They walked on the beach and kept talking until it was almost evening, when they reached a cottage, some pilgrims came to meet Swamiji. Aval arrange to them, Swamaji introduces everything, and they introduced themselves. Young girls and boys ran about the beach. Engineer asked, “Why they were walking on seashore. Aval Engineer, “The area is infected with snakes, especially Russel’s vipers; didn’t neither you nor me requesting baahuji to keep awake? Walking along the water front is not that risky” (Bhatt 123). An engineer always respected Aval’s privacy, he never behind in the gossip. They have decided go trekky with youngsters to Ekaliya. There was a beautiful shrine in the Island. It is a wonderful shrine; it stood on a back platform two or three feet high. At the distance, there was a haltered of four to five cows. Swamiji defined, religion means, “You may say, yes. It must have a nature, but that is like parroting from the books. Religion is faith in depth of a human heart. It has no name. To serve everything that breathes and to live in happiness; that’s religion” (Bhatt 132). An engineer departed to Patwa.

Oceanside Blues depicts the relationship between nature and human being and costal people and tribal strongly are believed in the nature and superstition. Sarvan brought a mail, Engineer received a letter from Parashar, and he would be coming to there for about five day between the twelfth and seventeenth June. Swamiji, the headman met him, his report is ready he worked on the report until the afternoon. The survey of land around Kheera had almost been completed. He was carrying the pile of mope in proper order during the late afternoon. Noor-bhaai also arrived there, he said, “All my life I lived in the wild. Allah the Great sent me to live at on earth a barren spot but gave me the task of growing jangles. What else but a great boundary of the Alimighty” (Bhattt 137). Engineer made him to sit there. Parashar has arrived; he shared his

experience, “Two years ago, on my arrival. I was repelled by this land. Now I intensely wished my friends would come and settle here. There was the magic spell cast by the earth. May be this was what they called, maayaa, an enchanting illusion. Two years’ stay here had transformed me from a city-dweller into an inhabitant of a barren countryside, an Oceanside creator” (Bhatt 138). Parashar and Angineer had decided to visit to Bhenasala. He sends Sarvan to Varaah-Swaroop to bring fishing boat. As soon as arrival of a fishy boat, they walked to the landing stage. Sarvan carried baggage. They have started a journey, they saw Aval panting and running towards them with Vishno in the crook of her arm. She hold the rope, she said, “Snake stung Vishno”. They carried him but Aval said, “He must be taken to the dargaah on the isle immediately. Fakir-baapu heals snakebites” (Bhatt 144). He was surprised “to hear Aval wanting to resort to a superstitions ritual for curing snakebite” (Bhatt 144). He said, “What can be done at the dargaah? We better take him to a doctor” (Bhatt 144). Finally, they launched a boat and boarded, Aval, Vishno and Parashar, are sitting he said, “What as a fakir or a witchdoctor do?” (Bhatt 144). Aval became angry and said, ‘Whatever happens will be God’s will as his mother. I want to be satisfied of having done all I could have” (Bhatt 144). She has that confidence and believed in superstition, “Of course not, my son! You’re going to be fine very soon. I have already localized the string by cutting the blood vessels and trying the string. Do you know what it is? It’s called a tourniquet. How anything can happens to you now? And Fakir-baaba will cure you in no time” (Bhatt 145). They reached dargaah. Fakir ignited the holy incense, he began to brush Vishno’s body, head to the tow with a bunch of peacocks feathers and recite holy verses. Nikhil give the modern medicine, Aval said, “We shall manage” (Bhatt 147). Engineer, Parashar crossed the creek. There was a sad story of Aval. Gopal was telling the story of Aval. Aval’s husband was living at Patwa, one day, he was disappeared. Keshav is relative of Aval.

One day, in midsummer month of Vaishaakh Lord Hanuman appeared, in Keshav's dream and said, "My devotee, I'd draw water from well for your guests and won't cistern near well remain empty even for a movement until all of them left for home" (Bhatt 150). Parashar think that he is a fool. The haveli is a belonging to Haada Bhatt. The tribes depend upon the forest products. Noor-bhaai had remembered and seen when he was a child "Today nothing remained except the Kabul thickets" (Bhatt 162). In the name of progress and prosperity destroyed everything.

Oceanside Blue depicts the result of Ocean God's displeasure. She sends Sarvan to fetch all kids, Avala look after everyone. Engineer heard of a cyclone, it was developing in the Arabian sea and there was a climate change. Sea was angry, there were big waves. The tempest had been rising unabated for the last seventeen or eighteen hours. Aval distributes jagrery, groundnuts, gram beans and puffed rice children ate and stay in the Bungalow. It was submerged; they went upstairs and stood on the terrace. It looks like a shipwreck in the high seas. A curfew was imposed; fear and hunger had gripped the city. Helicopter was flying on a terrace; it turned and circled over repeatedly. The helicopter steadied over the Havel and jettisoned plastic covered packets. Sarvan and Engineer ran out, gathered the food packets, brought them, and distribute to children. Floodwater swirled all around the storm-stricken building. In Patwa many houses had collapsed, there were no human casualties. Noor-Bhaai was no more, entire town was destroyed.

Oceanside Blue depicts the government project implementation. The Havel is belongs to Aval, he asked Aval, “After going back to the city, I can file your claim to the haveli in a court of law. I have many documents to substantiate your claim” (Bhatt 176). But there was no good respect from her, she asked about natural heir. Then, he revealed that Gopal’s story. The Green belt project was implemented, the saplings arrived by cartloads and the planting commenced. Sobar and his wife started the work in the field.

Work Cited

Bhatt, Dhruv. *Oceanside Blues*. Translation. Vinod Meghani. New Delhi: Sahitya Akadani, 2001.